

NODES

Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Report on heat stress monitoring and quantification

SPOKE N 6 Primary Agroindustry

Flagship project FORMIDABILÆ

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

A) Heat stress quantification

The aim of the research was to analyze the effects of heat wave on resilience indices and production parameters of dairy cows, so that these effects are examined quantitatively along three axes: (1) differences between primiparous and multiparous cows; (2) stages of lactation; and (3) baseline levels of milk production. We hypothesize that physiological differences, lactation stage, and initial production level play key roles in the amount of decline and the time to recovery of dairy cow performance during heat wave, and that understanding these differences can inform breeding and sustainable dairy cow management in the era of climate change.

DATA COLLECTION

To investigate milk yield resilience to heat wave in dairy cows, data from 305 dairy cows from four commercial farms located in Arborea (Italy) were used; all of these farms experienced the heat wave that occurred from 12 to 19 August 2022. The farms were equipped with automatic milking systems (AMS) and, for each cow, daily data including days in milk (DIM), parity, and daily milk yield were recorded during the period from 1 to 31 August 2022. From the initial dataset, only records from cows with parity 1 to 5 were selected, and cows with parity ≥ 6 were excluded. Also, cows with DIM > 350 at the beginning of August were excluded from the study. To ensure data quality and completeness, we included only cows with continuous daily records covering the August 1 to 30, 2022 window. Eligibility required a first record on or before August 2 and a last record on or after August 29. To identify outliers, the mean and standard deviation of daily milk yield during the observation period were calculated for each cow. If there was even one value in the records of a cow that was more than three standard deviations away from that cow's mean milk yield, all records of that cow were excluded from the final analysis to avoid the influence of abnormal values and possible data-entry errors. Also, cows that produced less than 1 kg/day of milk or had an average daily milk yield of less than 10 kg/day (signs of culling, dry-off, or disease) for more than five days during the observation period were also excluded. For data analysis, statistical grouping was performed as follows; the cows included in the study were divided into two groups based on parity, primiparous (parity = 1) and multiparous (parity ≥ 2). Also, according to DIM, the lactation stage of each cow was categorized into three classes, early lactation (DIM ≤ 100), mid lactation ($101 \leq \text{DIM} \leq 200$), and late lactation (DIM > 200). In addition, cows were classified into three groups based on their average baseline milk yield in the period before the heat wave, low-producing (less than 32.84 kg), medium-producing (32.84 to 39.24 kg), and high-producing (more than 39.24 kg). This division was based on the lower, middle, and upper terciles of the distribution of baseline milk yield values.

RECORDING AND CALCULATION OF ENVIRONMENTAL DATA

Based on the data collected in 2022, an intense summer heat wave occurred in August. Environmental data on dry-bulb temperature (Tdb) and relative humidity (RH) were recorded hourly at each farm by dedicated data loggers from 1 to 31 August 2022, and the THI was calculated based on the following equation proposed by the National Research Council:

$$THI = [1.8 \times Tdb + 32] - (0.55 - (0.0055 \times RH)) \times (1.8 \times Tdb - 26) \quad (1)$$

where Tdb is the dry-bulb temperature (in degrees Celsius) and RH is the relative humidity (in percent). The daily mean THI for each farm was then obtained and used in the analyses.

In August, the date with the maximum THI was considered the peak of the wave, with the wave starting at THI 74.7 on August 12 and ending with THI 74.4 on August 19 (Table 1). The number of days the heat wave lasted is shown in the Figures below. On average, cows showed a decrease in milk yield during and after the heat wave, confirming that the selected heat wave was appropriate for studying individual cow responses in milk production.

CALCULATION OF RESILIENCE INDICES AND MILK PRODUCTION TRAITS

In this study, we calculated ten indices to quantify the resistance and recovery of milk production during the heat wave. The exact definitions and formulas for each index are provided in Table 2. Together, these indices allow a comprehensive assessment of dairy cows' ability to tolerate and recover from heat stress, informing strategies to mitigate its negative effects on milk production.

Statistical Analysis

To examine the effect of various factors on heat wave response indices, a linear mixed-effects model (LMM) was used. All statistical analyses were performed in R (version 4.3.2) using specialized packages, including lme4 for fitting models via the lmer function, the emmeans package for calculating and extracting estimated marginal means (EMMs; formerly LSMeans), and the multcomp package for multiple comparisons and statistical grouping. The statistical model used for each index was as follows:

$$Index_{\{ijkl\}} = \mu + ParityGroup_i + LactationStage_j + MilkBeforeHW_k + Herd_l + \varepsilon_{\{ijkl\}}$$

Where:

- $Index_{\{ijkl\}}$ = value of the response index to the heat wave for the corresponding cow
- μ = overall mean
- $ParityGroup_i$ = fixed effect of parity group (primiparous or multiparous)
- $LactationStage_j$ = fixed effect of lactation stage (early, mid, late)
- $MilkBeforeHW_k$ = fixed effect of baseline milk yield category before the heat wave (Low, Medium, High)
- $Herd_l$ = random effect to account for heterogeneity between herds
- $\varepsilon_{\{ijkl\}}$ = random error term

After fitting the above statistical model for each index, estimated marginal means were calculated using the emmeans package to compare the mean of the indices at different levels of the influencing factors. These means provide adjusted and comparable values for each group with respect to other model variables and provide the most accurate estimate of the true mean of each group.

For statistical comparisons between different groups (parity, lactation stage, baseline milk-yield category), multiple comparisons were conducted using Tukey's HSD, and letter-based grouping was performed using the multcomp package. To examine the relationship between response indices and environmental conditions, including mean temperature–humidity index (THI) and mean ambient temperature, the Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated along with the p-value separately for each group (parity, lactation stage, and baseline milk-yield category). These analyses were performed using the cor.test function in R, and significance levels were reported separately for each group combination. In all statistical analyses, a significance level of $p < 0.05$ was considered the criterion for detecting a significant difference or relationship between groups

RESULTS

The effect of heat wave on resilience indices and milk production traits in primiparous and multiparous dairy cows is shown in Table 3. There was no significant difference between primiparous and multiparous cows for milk loss percentage ($p = 0.798$). There was also no difference between primiparous and multiparous cows for area milk loss (kg; $p = 0.153$) and area loss percent ($p = 0.245$). There was no significant difference between primiparous and multiparous cows for minimum milk (kg/day; $p = 0.484$). Multiparous cows had a higher recovery milk (kg/day) than primiparous cows ($p = 0.001$), and although multiparous cows had a higher recovery milk percentage than primiparous cows, the difference was not significant ($p = 0.263$). Mean end-of-wave milk yield tended to increase for multiparous cows compared to primiparous cows ($p = 0.093$). Three-time indices, including Time to min (days), Recovery time (days), and Total stress duration (days), were not significantly different between primiparous and multiparous cows.

The correlations of THI and temperature with resilience and resilience indices and milk production traits in primiparous and multiparous dairy cows during a heat wave are shown in Table 4. Among the studied indices, several moderate and significant correlations were observed between THI or temperature and resilience/productive traits. In primiparous cows, THI showed moderate and significant positive correlations with minimum milk (kg/day; $r = 0.30$, $p = 0.00$), recovery milk (kg/day; $r = 0.34$, $p < 0.001$), and milk end HW (kg; $r = 0.34$, $p < 0.001$). In addition, temperature was significantly correlated with minimum milk (kg/day; $r = 0.23$, $p = 0.02$), recovery milk (kg/day; $r = 0.32$, $p < 0.001$), and milk end HW (kg; $r = 0.30$, $p = 0.001$). In multiparous cows, THI was significantly correlated with milk loss rate ($r = 0.23$, $p = 0.001$), time to

minimum milk ($r = 0.17$, $p = 0.02$), and recovery milk ($r = 0.26$, $p < 0.001$). Temperature was also significantly correlated with milk loss ($r = 0.21$, $p = 0.00$), milk recovery ($r = 0.18$, $p = 0.01$), and milk end HW (kg; $r = 0.15$, $p = 0.04$). For the remaining parameters, the correlations between THI or temperature and the measured traits were generally weak and not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

The effect of heat wave on resilience indices and milk production traits across lactation stages in dairy cows is shown in Table 5. The lowest milk loss (%) was observed in early lactation stage cows, which was not significantly different from mid lactation stage cows, but was significantly different from late lactation stage cows. No significant difference was observed between cows in different lactation stages for area milk loss (kg; $p = 0.197$). The lowest area loss percent was found in early lactation stage cows, which was not significantly different from mid lactation stage cows, but was significantly different from late lactation stage cows. The lowest values for minimum milk (kg/day) were observed in late and mid lactation stage cows, which were significantly different from early lactation stage cows. For recovery milk (kg/day), recovery percent (%), and milk end HW (kg), early lactation stage cows showed a significant increase compared to late and mid lactation stage cows, while there was no significant difference between late and mid lactation stage cows. For the two-time indices, including time to min (days) and recovery time (days), there was no significant difference between cows in different lactation stages ($p > 0.05$). The lowest total stress duration (days) was observed in early lactation stage cows, which was significantly different from late and mid lactation stage cows.

The correlations of THI and temperature with resilience indices and milk production traits across lactation stages in dairy cows during a heat wave are shown in Table 6. In the early lactation stage, no strong and significant correlation ($p < 0.05$ and $|r| > 0.2$) was observed between the studied indices and THI or temperature. In the mid lactation stage, there was a negative and significant correlation between milk loss (%) and THI ($r = -0.26$, $p = 0.01$). Additionally, a positive and significant correlation was observed between minimum milk (kg/day) and temperature ($r = 0.23$, $p = 0.02$), and between recovery milk (kg/day) and THI ($r = 0.21$, $p = 0.03$). In late lactation cows, recovery milk (kg/day) was positively and significantly correlated with both THI ($r = 0.43$, $p < 0.001$) and temperature ($r = 0.45$, $p < 0.001$). Milk end HW (kg) was also positively and significantly correlated with temperature ($r = 0.26$, $p = 0.00$). Time to min (days) was positively and significantly correlated with THI ($r = 0.24$, $p = 0.01$), whereas recovery time (days) was negatively and significantly correlated with THI ($r = -0.25$, $p = 0.01$).

The effect of heat wave on resilience indices and milk production traits across baseline milk yield in dairy cows is shown in Table 7. For milk loss percentage (milk loss %), there was no significant difference between cows with low, medium, and high production ($p = 0.407$). The highest cumulative milk loss (area milk loss (kg)) was observed in cows with high production, which was significantly different from cows with low and medium production ($p = 0.007$). However, for cumulative milk loss percentage (%), there was no significant difference between the different milk production groups ($p = 0.270$). The values of minimum milk production

(kg/day), recovery milk (kg/day), and milk production at the end of the heat wave (milk end HW (kg)) were significantly different between the low, medium, and high groups ($p < 0.001$), with the highest values observed in cows with high milk production. For time to minimum (days) and recovery time (days), there was no significant difference between the different milk production groups. The lowest value for total stress duration (days) was observed in cows with low production, which was significantly different from cows with medium and high production ($p < 0.001$).

The correlation of THI and temperature with resilience indices and milk production traits across baseline milk yield in dairy cows during a heat wave is shown in Table 8. In cows with low milk production, a significant negative correlation was observed between milk loss (%) and both THI ($r = -0.22$, $p = 0.03$) and temperature ($r = -0.24$, $p = 0.01$). A significant positive correlation was also found between minimum milk yield (kg/day) and THI ($r = 0.21$, $p = 0.04$). Recovery milk (kg/day) had a significant positive correlation with both THI ($r = 0.25$, $p = 0.01$) and temperature ($r = 0.22$, $p = 0.03$). In cows with medium milk production, there was a positive and significant correlation between milk loss (%) and THI ($r = 0.25$, $p = 0.01$). Additionally, both the cumulative amount of milk loss (area milk loss; kg; $r = 0.23$, $p = 0.02$) and the cumulative percentage of milk loss (area loss percent; %; $r = 0.23$, $p = 0.02$) were positively and significantly correlated with THI. In this group, a negative and significant correlation was obtained between minimum milk yield (kg/day) and THI ($r = -0.24$, $p = 0.02$). Time to min (days) was positively and significantly correlated with THI ($r = 0.25$, $p = 0.01$), while recovery time (days) was negatively and significantly correlated with THI ($r = -0.27$, $p = 0.01$). Recovery milk (kg/day) was also positively and significantly correlated with THI ($r = 0.20$, $p = 0.04$). In cows with high milk production, there was a positive and significant correlation between cumulative milk loss (area milk loss (kg)) and THI ($r = 0.20$, $p = 0.05$). Furthermore, cumulative milk loss percentage (area loss percent (%)) was positively and significantly correlated with temperature ($r = 0.21$, $p = 0.04$).

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of temperature humidity index and temperature during the main phases of the heat wave

Heat wave Phase	Temperature Humidity Index				Temperature			
	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Start of heat wave	74.7	0.6	73.7	75.3	25.4	0.01	25.4	25.5
Peak of heat wave	80.4	0.6	78.5	81.0	28.5	0.1	28.3	28.6
End of heat wave	74.4	0.4	73.9	75.1	25.6	0.2	25.5	26.4

Table 2. Resilience indices and milk production traits during the heat wave

Index	Definition
Milk loss	The percentage decrease in daily milk yield from the average of the 7 days before the heat wave to the lowest value recorded during the 8 days of the heat wave (days 0 to 7).
Area milk loss	The total amount of milk lost (in kilograms) over the 8 days of the heat wave (days 0 to 7), calculated as the area under the curve of decreased milk yield compared to the baseline.
Area loss percent	The percentage of the total milk lost (Area Milk Loss) relative to the baseline milk yield over the 8 days of the heat wave (days 0 to 7).
Minimum milk	The lowest daily milk yield recorded during the 8 days after the start of the heat wave (days 0 to 7).
Time to min	The number of days from the beginning of the heat wave until the minimum milk yield is reached (within days 0 to 7).
Recovery time	The number of days from the minimum milk yield (during the heat wave) until the first day when milk yield returns to or exceeds the baseline (before the heat wave), or the highest value during the recovery period.
Recovery milk	The highest daily milk yield recorded during the 7-day recovery period (days 8 to 14 after the start of the heat wave).
Recovery percent	The percentage of milk recovery at the end of the heat wave compared to the initial milk loss that is, how much of the lost milk was regained.
Milk end HW	The average milk yield during the last three days of the heat wave (days 6 to 8).
Total stress duration	The total number of days from the start of the heat wave until milk yield returns to the baseline or higher (or the day of maximum recovery).

Table 3. Effect of heat wave on resilience indices and milk production traits in primiparous and multiparous dairy cows

parameters	Primiparous	Multiparous	P value
Milk loss (%)	20.4 ± 4.23	20.8 ± 20.8	0.798
Area milk loss (kg)	16.9 ± 3.14	19.3 ± 3.06	0.153
Area loss percent (%)	5.91 ± 1.10	6.58 ± 1.08	0.245
Minimum milk (kg/day)	29.1 ± 1.61	29.6 ± 1.58	0.484
Time to min (days)	4.03 ± 0.29	3.89 ± 0.26	0.631
Recovery time (days)	5.45 ± 0.39	5.45 ± 0.42	0.989
Recovery milk (kg/day)	41.3 ± 2.30 ^a	43.7 ± 2.28 ^b	0.001
Recovery percent (%)	40.4 ± 14.3	57.3 ± 12.8	0.263
Milk end HW (kg)	35.4 ± 1.14	36.4 ± 1.11	0.093
Total stress duration (days)	9.46 ± 0.44	9.33 ± 0.43	0.479

Parity groups were defined as: Primiparous (parity = 1) and Multiparous (parity ≥ 2).

Table 4. Correlation of THI and temperature with resilience indices and milk production traits in primiparous and multiparous dairy cows during a heat wave

parameters	Group							
	Primiparous				Multiparous			
	THI	P value	Temp	P value	THI	P value	Temp	P value
Milk loss (%)	-0.15	0.11	-0.05	0.59	0.05	0.48	0.01	0.93
Area milk loss (kg)	-0.05	0.58	0.01	0.91	0.23	0.00	0.21	0.00
Area loss percent (%)	-0.15	0.12	-0.06	0.52	0.11	0.13	0.10	0.16
Minimum milk (kg/day)	0.30	0.00	0.23	0.02	0.08	0.26	0.03	0.66
Time to min (days)	0.11	0.25	0.14	0.13	0.17	0.02	-0.05	0.51
Recovery time (days)	-0.15	0.11	-0.17	0.07	-0.13	0.07	-0.03	0.63
Recovery milk (kg/day)	0.34	<0.001	0.32	<0.001	0.26	<0.001	0.18	0.01
Recovery percent (%)	0.08	0.38	0.04	0.71	-0.05	0.48	-0.03	0.65
Milk end HW (kg)	0.34	<0.001	0.30	0.00	0.11	0.14	0.15	0.04
Total stress duration (days)	-0.11	0.26	-0.10	0.29	0.03	0.66	-0.13	0.08

Parity groups were defined as: Primiparous (parity = 1) and Multiparous (parity ≥ 2).

Table 5. Effect of heat wave on resilience indices and milk production traits across lactation stages in dairy cows

parameters	Early	Mid	Late	P value
Milk loss (%)	17.7 ± 4.36 ^a	20.4 ± 4.23 ^{ab}	23.6 ± 4.27 ^b	0.033
Area milk loss (kg)	16.0 ± 3.30	19.6 ± 3.14	18.8 ± 3.19	0.197
Area loss percent (%)	5.04 ± 1.16 ^a	6.69 ± 1.10 ^{ab}	7.01 ± 1.12 ^b	0.024
Minimum milk (kg/day)	31.5 ± 1.66 ^b	28.9 ± 1.61 ^a	27.6 ± 1.63 ^a	<0.001
Time to min (days)	3.63 ± 0.35	4.04 ± 0.29	4.21 ± 0.31	0.336
Recovery time (days)	5.19 ± 0.47	5.50 ± 0.42	5.67 ± 0.44	0.583
Recovery milk (kg/day)	45.5 ± 2.35 ^b	41.8 ± 2.31 ^a	40.3 ± 2.32 ^a	<0.001
Recovery percent (%)	83.7 ± 17.1 ^b	28.4 ± 14.3 ^a	34.4 ± 15.5 ^a	0.008
Milk end HW (kg)	38.6 ± 1.20 ^b	35.2 ± 1.14 ^a	33.9 ± 1.16 ^a	<0.001
Total stress duration (days)	8.78 ± 0.45 ^a	9.51 ± 0.43 ^b	9.90 ± 0.44 ^b	<0.001

Lactation stages were defined as: Early (DIM ≤ 100 days), Mid (101 ≤ DIM ≤ 200 days), and Late (DIM > 200 days).

Figure 1. Effect of parity and daily mean THI on milk yield during the heat wave

Figure 2. Effect of parity and daily mean temperature on milk yield during the heat wave

Figure 3. Effect of lactation stage and daily mean THI on milk yield during the heat wave

Figure 4. Effect of lactation stage and daily mean temperature on milk yield during the heat wave

Figure 5. Effect of pre-heatwave milk yield level and daily mean THI on milk yield during the heat wave

Figure 6. Effect of pre-heatwave milk yield level and daily mean temperature on milk yield during the heat wave

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B) Predicting daily milk yield during heat waves based on weather forecast using linear model and machine-learning models: internal and external validation and an operational shiny application

INTRODUCTION

With global warming and the increase in the occurrence and intensity of heat waves, both in terms of frequency and duration (Wankar et al., 2021), agricultural yields have been affected, and the increased exposure of dairy cows to heat stress has led to a decrease in milk yield (Nascimento et al., 2025). In dairy farms, high-producing cows are the most sensitive group to heat stress due to genetic selection for higher production, a higher metabolic rate, and limited heat dissipation capacity (Wankar et al., 2021). Heat stress not only causes a decrease in milk yield but is also associated with changes in milk composition, reproductive disorders, impaired immune function, and reduced animal welfare (Giannone et al., 2023). Accurate and comparable measurement of milk yield declines and recoveries during heat waves is a key challenge; in this regard, the use of regression models and machine learning algorithms allows a more accurate analysis of the behavioral response of dairy cows to heat stress.

The aim of this study is to predict daily milk yield under heat wave conditions using a set of variables including the same-day heat stress index (THI) and short-term time windows (3- and 7-day averages and the previous day's value), short-term milk production history (the previous day's value and the 3-day average), and animal-based variables (lactation stage and parity group).

For this purpose, a linear regression model and several machine learning algorithms (Random Forest, Extreme Gradient Boosting, and Gradient Boosting Machine) were used to investigate the possibility of nonlinear or threshold patterns in addition to linear relationships.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Data collection

To predict milk yield during a heat wave in dairy cows, data from four commercial farms located in Arborea (Italy) were used; all of these farms experienced a heat wave that occurred in August 2022. The farms were equipped with automated milking systems (AMS), and for each cow, daily data including days in milk (DIM), parity, and daily milk yield were recorded during the period 1–31 August 2022.

From the initial dataset, only records from cows with parity numbers 1–5 were selected, and cows with parity numbers ≥ 6 were excluded. Also, cows with DIM greater than 350 at the

beginning of August were excluded from the study. To ensure data quality, we considered only cows whose continuous daily records covered the period 1–30 August 2022.

To identify outliers, the mean and standard deviation of daily milk yield during the observation period were calculated for each cow. If there was even one value in a cow's records more than three standard deviations away from that cow's average milk yield, all records of that cow were excluded from the final analysis to avoid the influence of abnormal values and possible data entry errors. Also, cows that produced less than 1 kg of milk per day or had an average daily milk yield of less than 10 kg per day (signs of culling, drying-off, or disease) for more than five days during the observation period were excluded.

The cows under study were divided into two groups based on the number of parities: primiparous (parity = 1) and multiparous (parity ≥ 2). Also, based on DIM, the lactation stage of each cow was divided into three categories: early lactation (DIM ≤ 100), mid lactation (101 ≤ DIM ≤ 200), and late lactation (DIM > 200).

Recording and calculation of environmental data

Based on the data collected in 2022, an extreme summer heat wave occurred in August. Environmental data on dry-bulb temperature (Tdb) and relative humidity (RH) were recorded hourly at each farm by dedicated data loggers from 1 to 31 August 2022, and THI was calculated based on the following equation proposed by the National Research Council:

$$\text{THI} = [(1.8 \times \text{Tdb} + 32) - (0.55 - (0.0055 \times \text{RH})) \times (1.8 \times \text{Tdb} - 26)] \quad (1)$$

where Tdb is the dry-bulb temperature (in degrees Celsius) and RH is the relative humidity (in percent). The daily mean THI for each farm was then obtained and used in the analyses.

Model development

The study was conducted in two steps: (1) internal validation using data from three merged farms (Casadei, Lai, and Panetto) and (2) external validation on an independent farm (Zirone). The purpose of external validation was to assess the generalizability of the model to “unseen” farms and cows and to avoid overfitting. The data included daily milk yield (MilkYield), heat stress index (THI), days in milk (DIM), cow identifier, and farm. For each cow, time-based, leak-free features were constructed from the past only: previous day's production (Milk_lag1), 3-day rolling average of production (Milk_roll3), previous day's THI (THI_lag1), 3-day rolling average of THI (THI_roll3), and 7-day rolling average of THI (THI_roll7). Group variables included parity group (Primiparous; Multiparous) and lactation stage based on DIM (Early: ≤100 days; Mid: 101–200; Late: >200).

The GLM (fixed-effects linear model) was fitted with the above inputs; as a comparison, three machine learning algorithms, Random Forest (RF), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGB), and Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM) were used to investigate potential nonlinear or threshold relationships in the data. To avoid leakage, temporal preprocessing (lag/roll) was performed separately on the training/test sets, and for GLM/GBM/XGB, the numerical variables were standardized using the mean and standard deviation of the training set. In the internal

validation step, cow-wise 80/20 splits were used repeatedly to ensure that each cow's records were placed in only one of the two sets (training or testing). Evaluation criteria included R^2 (coefficient of determination), RMSE (root mean square error), and CCC (Lin's concordance correlation coefficient). Then, in the external validation step, the fitted models were fully evaluated on the Zirone farm without any retraining. Analyses were performed in RStudio with the packages corresponding to each model and algorithm and for plotting.

Shiny app development

Data from three farms (Casadei, Lai, and Panetto) were used for the final training. Features were built in a cow-centric manner and derived solely from past records. The final models and their metadata were saved as RDS files. For each model (GLM, RF, XGB, GBM), the forecast of milk yield for the following day is reported. The application was published via shinyapps.io.

RESULTS

The internal evaluation results for the GLM, GBM, XGB, and RF models are presented in Table 1, and the observation–prediction comparison plots are shown in Figure 1. In this set, GLM showed the best performance, achieving the lowest RMSE (4.145) and the highest R^2 (0.843) and CCC (0.915). As can be seen in Figure 1-A, the cloud of points is centered around the line $y=x$, indicating good calibration and a strong correlation between the observed and predicted values. The GBM and XGB algorithms performed very similarly and slightly worse than GLM, and RF provided the lowest accuracy in this evaluation ($R^2 = 0.831$; RMSE = 4.306; CCC = 0.907).

Table 1. Internal cross-validation results for the GLM, GBM, XGB, and RF models¹

Model	R^2	RMSE	CCC
GLM	0.843	4.145	0.915
GBM	0.840	4.192	0.913
XGB	0.838	4.214	0.911
RF	0.831	4.306	0.907

¹ GLM, General linear model with fixed effects; GBM, Gradient boosting machine; XGB, Extreme gradient boosting; RF, Random forest; R^2 , Coefficient of determination; RMSE, Root mean square error; CCC: Lin's concordance correlation coefficient

Figure 1. Observed vs. Predicted Milk Yield: (A) GLM, (B) GBM, (C) XGB, (D) RF.

The external validation results for the GLM, GBM, XGB, and RF models are shown in Table 2. GLM performed best, achieving the lowest RMSE (1.021) and the highest R^2 (0.981) and CCC (0.991). Compared with the closest machine-learning algorithms, the RMSE was about 19 -20% lower. XGB and RF performed very similarly, with GBM slightly weaker than both ($R^2 = 0.971$; RMSE = 1.268; CCC = 0.986). Unlike the internal evaluation, the ranking of the machine-learning algorithms in the external validation was not exactly replicated; nevertheless, GLM remained the most stable and accurate model.

Table 2. External validation (farm-out) results for GLM, GBM, XGB, and RF¹

Model	R^2	RMSE	CCC
GLM	0.981	1.021	0.991
GBM	0.971	1.268	0.986
XGB	0.972	1.258	0.986
RF	0.972	1.259	0.986

¹ GLM, General linear model with fixed effects; GBM, Gradient boosting machine; XGB, Extreme gradient boosting; RF, Random forest; R^2 , Coefficient of determination; RMSE, Root mean square error; CCC: Lin's concordance correlation coefficient

The advantage of GLM in this research stems from the close match between its assumptions and the structure of the predictor–response relationship: daily milk changes are mainly

explained by short-term autoregressive terms and the additive effects of THI, along with two categorical factors (Parity and Lactation Stage). Over the observed range these relationships are approximately linear and show no strong interactions, so GLM yields stronger performance with low complexity, lower estimation variance, and better calibration.

By contrast, tree and boosting algorithms (GBM, XGB, and RF) must make multiple splits to approximate the same linear function, which can lead to over-smoothing; with limited sample size and tuning they also fail to extract benefits from true nonlinearity. Moreover, trees inherently do not extrapolate and are limited to the leaf mean in the distribution tails, whereas GLM continues linearly (Hastie et al., 2009). As a result, the advantage of more complex structures is lost here, and GLM shows consistent superiority in RMSE, R^2 , and CCC.

To make the linear model and machine learning algorithms in this research applicable to dairy farms, a tool has been developed in Shiny using the obtained data, which allows the user to view milk yield predictions by entering features. This program is available at the following address: https://animalanalyzer.shinyapps.io/milk_app/

Figure 2. Shiny app

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